

Variational Autoencoder Latent Spaces as a Powerful Framework for Protein Evolution and Design

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The vast sequence space of proteins presents a significant challenge in protein design, as only a tiny fraction of possible sequences are functional. Evolutionary principles help navigate this immense space by focusing on protein family-related sites and mutations, effectively constraining design efforts to functionally relevant regions. Ancestral sequence reconstruction (ASR) is a powerful method for evolutionary-based protein design, using homologous sequences in a multiple sequence alignment and an inferred phylogenetic tree to reconstruct ancestral nodes. However, ASR remains a labour-intensive process, requiring numerous manual steps. Generative machine learning models provide a promising avenue for designing enhanced proteins by leveraging techniques from natural language processing to decipher essential evolutionary patterns from large datasets of amino acid sequences. While generative models have been helpful for protein design, there remains a limited understanding of introducing beneficial mutations without disrupting function [1]. On the other hand, complex protein evolution data provides a powerful tool for extracting meaningful information automatically.

This study introduces the latent spaces of variational autoencoders (VAEs) and sampling strategies to generate variants resembling ancestral sequences from multiple sequence alignments of specific protein families. To this end, we optimized the VAE architecture to capture evolutionary dependencies in the latent space geometry. We found two dimensions and a single dense layer sufficient to reconstruct close ancestral variants of given protein families. We employed sampling strategies of sequence mutagenesis, latent space evolutionary trajectories, and multi-objective optimization. We used the evolutionary trajectory strategy on the haloalkane dehalogenases protein family and obtained variants with increased activity and stability [2]. Building upon this collected high-quality experimental data, we used structure and inverse fold predictors to examine protein foldability scores. We designed a sampling strategy aimed at generating sequences that jointly had high foldability scores and possessed traits of ancestral sequences, thus potentially improving the success rate of generated variants. The VAE strategy is available as an interactive module of the FireProtASR 2.0 tool: <https://loschmidt.chemi.muni.cz/fireprotasr2/>.

[1] Kouba P et al. Machine learning-guided protein engineering. ACS Catalysis 13:13863-95, 2023 <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acscatal.3c02743>.

[2] Kohout P et al. Engineering Dehalogenase Enzymes Using Variational Autoencoder-Generated Latent Spaces and Microfluidics. JACS Au 2025 <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/jacsau.4c01101>.

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